

Food Security, Livelihoods Improvement and Ecological Sustainability of Wetland: A case study of Mpondi Wetland in Milola Lindi –Tanzania.

Globally wetlands contribute in diverse ways to ecosystem services, food security and livelihoods. With such crucial roles, their production capacity has declined due to multiple reasons as a result of decline in ecosystem services. This paper presents findings from an assessment aimed at gaining a deeper understanding of how the Mpondi Wetland contributes to ecological functions, food security, and community livelihoods. It assessed the contribution of the Mpondi wetland to food security and livelihoods, as well as community awareness regarding conservation of the wetland. The study was conducted in the Mpondi Wetland, located in Milola–Lindi Municipal, and included a total of five villages as its sampling frame. Questionnaires, in-depth interviews, and observation methods were used to obtain information from the field. Qualitative data were analyzed using content analysis techniques, whereas quantitative data were analyzed using SPSS version 16.0, and the findings were presented using descriptive statistics. The study found that the Mpondi Wetland contributes greatly to ecosystem functions, food security, and livelihoods of households in Milola; however, the ecological status and crop production have declined. The main reasons for this decline include, but are not limited to, poor agricultural practices, the drying of the wetland due to climate change, and destruction of crops by wild animals (especially elephants). Therefore, the study demonstrates strategies for building climate change resilience in the agricultural sector as a key concern for rural communities in Tanzania and globally. Additionally, the study recommends adopting different approaches to the management of wetlands for the sustainable utilization of wetland resources.

Keywords:	Wetland, Ecology, Food Security, Livelihoods, Sustainability, conservation
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1. INTRODUCTION

People in different places face challenges in meeting their livelihoods and achieving food security, which has led to the encroachment of fragile environments like wetlands. (Babaniyi, Petkovic et al., 2010; NEMA, 2010). Globally, wetlands are of great significance to crop production. However, they are under threat because of overutilization and climate change. As a result, various international and local instruments have been devised to manage and protect them (Mulatu et al., 2015). These include the Ramsar Convention on Wetlands of 1971, which recognized wetlands as geographical areas of international importance, the Kyoto Protocol of 1995, United Nations Conference on Environment and Development (UNCED) in 1992 and the Copenhagen Climate Change Conference of 2009 (i.e. (Peimer et al., 2017).

Different countries around the world are reported to be troubled by food insecurity which is attributed to different reasons such as prolonged drought, regional conflicts, population growth, economic collapse and climate change (Salim et al., 2025). Climate change is changing productive areas to unproductive ones while high population growth is associated with land degradation due to overutilization of the resources available on the land (Leemhuis et al., 2017).

In 2019 two billion people, equivalent to 25.9 % of the global population, experienced hunger or did not have regular access to nutritious and sufficient food (WHO, 2020). Reports show that food insecurity has been declining globally, however, a large proportion of hungry people are reported in developing countries, where 1.03 billion people are in Asia, 675 million in Africa, 205 million in Latin America and the Caribbean, while Northern America and Europe have only 88 million (WHO, 2020). The decline in food insecurity has led many households engage in farming activities in the wetland areas, especially during the dry seasons and the seasons with low rainfall (Omay, 2024). The use of wetlands for agriculture has been associated with increased food security and improved livelihoods in various communities. For instance, the World Wetland Day report of 2nd February 2016 indicated that rice, which is grown in wetland areas, is the staple diet for more than half of the world's population and accounts for about 80% of the world's rice (Dixon et al., 2016).

The 2017 and 2018 editions of the Africa Regional Overview of Food Security and Nutrition, reported that about 256 million people were without sufficient food. 17million were in North

Africa while 239 million were in sub-Saharan Africa (WHO, 2020). Sub-Saharan Africa is reported to have the highest level of food insecurity and it has been shown that, if immediate measures are not taken, the future will be even worse (Wudil & Barrett, 2010). Food insecurity in the Sub-Saharan region is associated with rapid population growth and the impact of climate change which has made some areas that were used for crop cultivation earlier no longer useful due to drought.

Subsistence farmers have engaged in agricultural activities in wetland areas, especially in times of crop failure or drought (Marambanyika, 2021). For instance, in South Africa, a large number of households depend on wetland areas for grazing of their animals, crop production (i.e. maize, wheat, sugar cane, oats and sunflower) and construction of houses (Chatanga et al., 2020). Also, the White Nile wetland in South Sudan is reported to be used for grazing animals, fishing activities, building materials, and collecting medicinal plants and animal products, all of which enhance community livelihoods and food security (Dalahmeh et al., 2018).

In Tanzania, food insecurity has been reported in various regions and districts. A study conducted by Integrated Food Security Phase Classification (IPC) from November 2019 to April 2020 showed that over 20% of the population in sixteen districts under study were experiencing insufficiency of food and 10% of the households in those administrative regions were facing severe food insecurity (Shukla et al., 2021). The key factors for food insecurity were the unreliable rainfall characterized by late onset and early cessation during the planting season and prolonged dry spells in some areas, which hindered crop growth (Shukla et al., 2021).

About 80% of Tanzanians are living in rural areas where the main economic activity is rain-fed agriculture, which results in low yield, especially during the dry season (Mulungu et al., 2024). Since rural farmers cannot practice mechanized agriculture (irrigation and fertilizers), they opt to expand their agricultural land to fragile environments like wetland areas for their livelihood and food security. Farmers in Milola conduct crop cultivation in wetlands like Mkarakacha, Ngwenya and Mpondi wetlands for agricultural production. However, Mpondi wetland is highly utilized than other wetlands due to high fertility and wetness of the valley (TPP, 2020). Despite that the wetland contribute to food security and livelihoods for most of the Milola community, recently crop production in the wetland has declined. For this reason, the researcher chose Mpondi wetland to explore its current status of contribution to food security and household livelihoods. In defining livelihood, the study adopted the Sustainable Livelihood Approach by Robert Chambers of 1980s

which explain how the four aspects of livelihood affect human wellbeing; vulnerability context which include shocks like human, livestock or crop health, natural hazards like climate change impacts; livelihood assets which include natural capital like land, water, forests and biodiversity; transforming structures and processes which include institutions, organizations, policies and legislation that shape and monitor attainment of livelihoods and lastly is livelihood outcome which comprises the achievement of the livelihood strategies which include income generation, improvement of well-being, reduced vulnerability, and improvement in food security (Tambe,2022). In defining poverty this study adopted the FAO approach which focuses on four main dimensions of food security including Physical availability of food which addresses the “supply side” of food security and is determined by the level of food production, economic and physical access, access by individuals to adequate resources (entitlements) for acquiring appropriate foods for a nutritious diet; food utilization, utilization of food to reach a state of nutritional well-being where all physiological needs are met and stability of the other three dimensions over time (resistance from shocks) (FAO 2008).

The paper is organized into six main sections: an overview of the study, description of the study area, methodology, results, discussion, and conclusions with recommendations.

2. METHODOLOGY

Study area

This study was conducted in the Mpondi wetland in Milola B village in the Milola ward in the Lindi Region-Tanzania. The region has a population of about 1,194,028 (URT, 2022) and has a total of six districts, namely Kilwa, Liwale, Nachingwea, Luangwa, Lindi district council and Lindi municipal. Lindi municipal has a population of about 174,126 (84,078 men and 90,048 women) and an average household size of 3.3 (URT, 2022). The district has a total of 19 wards, which include Milola ward located at geographical coordinates 9⁰59'0" South and 39⁰24'0" East and has a population of about 12,516 (URT, 2022). Milola borders Nanguru ward to the East, Ilondo to the West, Kiwawa to the North and Lutamba to the South. The ward is located 60 km (23 square miles) from Lindi Municipal (TPP, 2020). The main ethnic groups found in Milola are Makonde, Mwera, Nghyindo and Yao (TPP, 2020). Milola was selected since is a rural ward where the dominant economic activity is agriculture (Bakuza, 2018) and about 92% of the households

earn their living through cultivation of crops like sesame, rice and maize which are grown in small farming plots and farmers conduct crop cultivation in wetlands like Mkarakacha, Ngwenya and Mpondi wetlands for agricultural production (TPP, 2020). Mpondi wetland is used by a total of four villages namely Milola Magharibi, Mkangaulani, Namtamba and Milola B since these are the villages which are closer to the wetland.

Figure 1 Map of the study area

Data collection and analysis

A sample of 100 heads of households (farmers) was randomly chosen from 1,050 households in four villages of Milola ward (23% Namtamba, 22% Milola Magharibi, 17% Mkangaulani, 38% Milola B), the number of respondents (10 %) in each village depended on the total number of households within the village, since a sample size of 10% of the population is considered sufficient for statistical power in research (Kothari, 2017). Random sampling was used so that the heads of households could have an equal chance of being selected for the sample, thus reducing bias in the

sampling process (Kothari, 2017). Non random sampling was applied to collect detailed information from key informants including the Village Executive Officer (VEO), the Ward Executive Officer WEO ‘, the District Agriculture Officer DAO ‘and District Environmental Officer DEO ‘. This study applied a mixed methods approach, where both quantitative and qualitative methods were used to gain a clear understanding of the research problem. The quantitative component was the dominant and was used to obtain primary data on socio-economic activities undertaken by villagers of Milola ward at Mpondi wetland, the community ‘s willingness to protect the wetland and the attitudes and perceptions of the people on the management of the wetland. The qualitative component was used to support the quantitative findings and was deployed to collect primary data on the contribution of Mpondi wetland to food security and livelihoods. The study area Map was drawn by using ArcGIS. The study employed questionnaires to collect primary data on the contribution of Mpondi wetland on food security, livelihood and social economic activities undertaken in the wetland as well as the community ‘s willingness to protect the wetland. Interviews were performed with the Municipal, ward and village officers to obtain primary data on contribution of Mpondi wetland in ensuring food security and on the condition and management of the wetland. wetland. Direct observation was used in collecting primary data on the current condition of the wetland, the economic activities conducted, the crops grown in the wetland and the conservation measures undertaking to conserve the area.

The quantitative data collected by using a questionnaire were analyzed using SPSS version 16. The analysis involved explaining the data in terms of descriptive statistics whereby the data were presented in charts, graphs and tables to show frequency and percentages of the findings. The qualitative data were analyzed using the thematic analysis technique, based on overarching categories of common data across multiple sources, where data were organized and analyzed based on themes. Thematic analysis was applied to support quantitative findings from quantitative analysis

3. RESULTS

Crops grown in the wetland

The findings indicate that sesame is a dominant crop grown in the wetland which accounts for about 32% of all crops. Other crops include maize (19%), rice (12%), cassava (14%), peas (6%)

and gardening (8%). Maize and rice are among of crops which are grown in the bottom of the valley (wet areas) while crops like sesame and cassava are grown in the upper part of the valley.

Figure 2 Crops grown in the wetland

Similar findings can be observed from the study conducted by Dalahmeh et al. (2018) which indicated that various crops are grown in wetlands along the White Nile like rice, maize, sorghum, banana, beans, paddy, groundnuts and vegetables. The only difference is that few crops are grown in Mpondi wetlands as indicated in figure 2. On the other hand, the findings from this study indicated that recently, most crops in the Mpondi wetland are grown in the wet season only because the wetland is becoming dry, and it is difficult to carry out agricultural activities in the dry season without irrigation as it was in the previous years. Drought has possibly reduced agricultural production as shown in Figure 3. A. Ward Officer explained that:

“...recently, most of these crops are grown during the wet season and it is difficult to carry out farming activities in Mpondi wetland during the dry season as they were in previous years, because the wetland is becoming dry...” (19/09/2021)

These findings from the interview are supported by the observation made in the wetland which showed that most of the crops seen in the valley were coconut trees, gardens and a small amount of maize and rice cultivated through hand irrigation using buckets, as evidenced in figure 52.

Furthermore, the study findings indicate that a large proportion of women engage in the production of food crops and gardening while a large proportion of men engage in cash crops. For instance,

19% of men and only 13% of women engage in sesame production which is a cash crop in Milola. Also, women seem to participate more in food crop production, especially gardening which employs about 6% of the women. Meanwhile, there is only 2% of men engage in gardening; similar trends have been reported in the study conducted by Dalahmeh et al. (2018) in White Nile in South Sudan, where the findings show that women mostly cultivate rice, maize, and vegetables while men engage much in the production of rice and sesame. Since much of the cultivation of food crops like maize and rice is conducted at the bottom of the valley, women might be more affected by the drought of the valley compared to men who cultivate cash crops like sesame in the upper part of the valley.

Production of crops in a year

The findings revealed that currently, Mpondi wetland contributes less to food production and peoples' livelihoods than it was in previous years, as indicated in table 1. This is inconsistent with the study by Munishi et al. (2016), which indicated that the wetland of the Little Ruaha Sub Catchment in Mufindi contributes to about 31% of the total annual food production per household. The study findings indicate that the maximum production of a single crop per household is approximately 5,000 kilograms (in local units, -gunia 50 where -1 gunia is equivalent to 100kg) while the minimal production is 9 kg as shown in figure table 1. Sesame production is higher (5000kg) compared to other crops, but it is mainly produced as a cash crop - a means for generating monetary income. On the other hand, the production of food crops is very low compared to the actual demand, which leads to food insecurity and shortage of income. Most of the interviewed respondents said that their harvests do not sustain them to the next harvest season. Accordingly, the findings revealed that 39% of the respondents could not afford to eat three meals per day as in table 2.

The findings from descriptive statistics of crops indicate that there is a maximum deviation in the production of crops. For instance, the average production of sesame per household in a year is 470.1 kg with a standard deviation of 754 kg, since sesame is a cash crop and its cultivation is costly, implies that its production is dominated by few people who can cultivate and produce crops at a large scale while the majority (poor people) produces at a small scale. This is also evidenced in other crops as shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Descriptive statistics of crops production

Crop	No respondents	Average (kg)	Minimum (kg)	Maximum (kg)	Standard Deviation (kg)
Maize	70	164.71	15	1500	200.922
Rice	8	270	50	660	236.4
Sesame	46	470.11	15	5000	754.004
Cassava	32	84.50	9	600	120.002
Peas	19	78.16	10	500	114.349

Data indicating how crop production diverges from the mean production

Sale of wetland products for cash

The findings showed that the Wetland indirectly contributes to food security by serving as arable land for the production of cash crops which are sold to buy food. The study findings indicated that most of the households opt to cultivate sesame (a cash crop) which constitutes 58% of the respondents, day labor (28%) and gardening (8%) as a means of generating monetary income during food crop failure for purchasing food since most of the respondents reported that the harvested crops do not sustain their households to the next harvest season. This corroborates with the findings of the study conducted by Chepkwonyet al., (2019) in Kenya around Lake Kingwal wetland which indicated that about 60% of the respondents harvested agricultural products from the wetland and exchanged them with cash to buy food. In Milola, an average of 470 kg of sesame is produced in a season and 1 kg of sesame is worth Tsh 2250 (\$1). Hence, on average, sesame earns about TZS 1, 057,500 (\$459.8) for each household in a year.

Agricultural inputs

Even though farmers own large fields of land for crop cultivation they cultivate small portions of the land. More than 85% of respondents cultivate 1-5 acres in a year and a few of them can afford to cultivate 6+ acres. Cultivation of small portions of land is among the factors that contribute to the shortage of food (resulting in food insecurity) and income to sustain the households' needs. The main reason for farmers to cultivate small portions of land was the drought condition of the valley which creates a worry that they may get little output due to crop failure and lack of inputs. It was reported by 72% of the respondents that they cultivate small farms because they do not have

enough inputs. For instance, most of the respondents reported they use hand hoes as the only means to till the land, and 79% of the respondents do not apply industrial fertilizer in their farming activities. 79% of the respondents do not apply industrial fertilizer in their farming activities. Also, 15% of the respondents reported that they cultivate small portions of land due to a shortage of labor; most of those were women, especially divorced and widows. About 15% of the respondents are faced with a shortage of labor, whereby 13% of them were women and 2% were men.

Food security information

In Tanzania people are referred to as food insecure. The findings from this study indicate that 39% of the households take below three meals per day and only 61% of the respondents could afford to take three meals a day. This informs that there is food insecurity within the Milola community; despite that farmer producing their food, the harvested crops do not sustain their households. A large number of people in Milola are farmers which account for about 93% of the whole occupations, only 56% of the farmers could afford to eat three meals and more than 37% could not afford to eat three meals a day which might be caused by low productivity of agricultural harvest.

Furthermore, the study findings indicated that most households take much starch since cassava and maize are their main food crops produced as indicated in Figure 2. Also, lipid is taken to some extent due to the presence of coconuts farm plot as was revealed during observation of the crops grown in the wetland. Protein is taken in a small amount since most of the households in Milola are farmers (93%) with little domestication and the production of rice (12%) is at the lowest scale due to drying of the wetland.

Table: 2 Frequency of Meal per Day by Occupation

Occupation	Meal per Day			Percentage
	Once	Twice	Thrice	
Farmers	5	32	56	93
Livestock keepers	0	1	0	1
Employee	0	0	3	3
Petty traders	0	1	2	3
Percentage	5	34	61	100

Socio-economic activities undertaken at Mpondi wetland

Wetlands are known to be useful in different social economic activities for human livelihoods and food security. The findings from this study indicate that the Mpondi wetland is mainly utilized for agricultural production, this is different from the findings by Emerton (2015) which revealed that the wetland of the Nile River in South Sudan provides an area for grazing animals, fisheries activities, building materials, medicinal plants and significantly for agricultural production.; During the observation method in most of the observed farm fields there were crops grown and no other activities were evidenced apart from agriculture. It was supported by the findings from a key informant who commented:

‘More than 90% of the wetlands in Milola are utilized for agriculture, especially cultivation of crops like maize and rice, also utilized for gardens and horticulture on a small scale (DAO).

Although agricultural practices are dominant in the wetland, most of the activities are carried out during the wet season, since recently the valley has been drying.

There are few agricultural activities during the dry season, especially gardening, as was observed in the valley. The findings from this study indicated that the Mpondi wetland is experiencing a decline in wetness compared to previous years due to deforestation and poor agricultural practices that disturb the ecology of the wetland. Much of the vegetation observed was yellow, indicating dry conditions, and very few water channels were observed, which is not normal in wetland areas. This is consistent with the findings of Bakenges (2014), who noted that wetlands have been under pressure from overutilization due to their fertility and wetness, which make them more prone to degradation and possible disappearance.

Figure 3 Farmer irrigating crops through bucket.

The reasons identified for the drying of the wetland include poor farming practices, especially deforestation during farm preparation, cultivation near water sources, and local irrigation through boreholes. A key respondent said that:

‘Previously, there were many coconut trees in the valley that made the soil maintain wetness for a long time but recently, trees have been cleared that make the sun rays to heat the surface directly’ (DEO, Lindi Municipal-interview statement, 2021).

This is the reason production has decreased every year. Many respondents stated that crop yields have declined compared to previous years, mainly due to the drying of the valley. Over 59% of the respondents suggested that the wetland productivity declined as a result of drought.

‘Productivity has been declining every year for instance, the previous years’ crops grown in Milola were used to feed Lindi town, Mtwara up to Dar es Salaam and they were cultivated both during the wet and dry seasons but for now, even the food to feed the Milola community is not enough’ (DAO, Lindi municipal-interview statement, 2021).

Additionally, data from published sources in Milola Ward indicate that production has been declining annually, for instance, a total of 769 tons of maize were harvested between 2000 and 2010, but production declined by 75 tons between 2010 and 2020. Rice production decreased from 430 tons (2000–2010) to 424 tons (2010–2020). There was also a steady decline in sesame from

65 tons (2000–2010) to 60 tons (2010–2020), while peas increased slightly from 35 tons (2000–2010) to 39 tons (2010–2020). The steady decline occurred because most of these crops do not depend on the wetness of the valley but are grown in dryland areas. This indicates food insecurity, as agricultural production continues to decrease while the population keeps increasing, as shown by regional population data as in figure 4.

Figure 4: Population data from Lindi Region from 2000 to 2020

Figure 5: Crops production from 2000-2010 and 2010-2020 in Milola ward.

Moreover, productivity has been declining because people continue practicing traditional farming ('kilimo cha mazoea') despite receiving technical advice from agricultural experts. Apart from drought-induced reduction in production, another factor identified during fieldwork was human–wildlife conflict. Milola is located near Selous Game Reserve which has made elephants invade human settlements and crops. Extensive crop damage caused by elephants has led to hunger in several households.:

'I have not harvested peas as you can see those standing sticks in the farm field'
(respondent no 13, Ngwenya sub-village, Milola village B-interview statement, 2021).

When the Ward Executive Officer (WEO) was asked about government measures to address human–elephant conflicts, he explained that the government has deployed six wildlife officers to handle elephant invasions. In addition, two individuals in each village have been trained to create 'elephant feces block,' establish beehives, and use special torches to deter elephants all aimed at protecting human settlements and crops. Despite these efforts, challenges remain, particularly the shortage of trained personnel, vehicle fuel and financial resources.

Community awareness to conservation

The findings indicate that most respondents were willing to participate in wetland conservation activities: 75% expressed willingness, while 25% were not willing. Women were found to be more willing to engage in conservation than men: 45% of the willing participants were women, compared to 30% men. This may be because most women depend on the wetland valley for subsistence crop cultivation, whereas men tend to cultivate cash crops in dryland areas. Consequently, women are more affected by the drought conditions in the valley. This highlights the need to educate farmers on sustainable farming practices that ensure the longevity of the wetland ecosystem. The majority of respondents (66%) were aware of measures to conserve the wetland, while 34% lacked such awareness. Some of proposed approaches were avoiding cultivating near water sources, plantation of trees proposed and avoiding deforestation. Previous studies show that cultivation in wetland areas without measures for their sustainability would lead to the degradation of the wetland. For instance, Pangani and Kilombero have undergone

degradation mainly due to agricultural activities and the establishment of settlements (MNRT, 2004). This calls for the adoption of better approaches for the rehabilitation of the wetland resources to increase its agricultural productivity enhance food security and improve the livelihoods of the community. Hence, adopting effective rehabilitation strategies is essential to enhance wetland productivity, improve food security, and sustain community livelihoods.

4. DISCUSSION

People's experience of food insecurity and livelihoods

The low socioeconomic status of most households indicates high vulnerability to food insecurity. As recommended by Carson et al., (2020) food insecurity is closely related to low-income people, especially in the agriculturally based rural society. Although Tanzania generally exhibits relative food security compared to other East African countries, food insecurity remains severe in rural areas where agriculture is predominantly rain-fed (Omay, 2024). Food insecurity in rural Tanzania is increasing due to factors such as climate change (droughts and prolonged rainfall leading to floods), shortage of agricultural inputs (like fertilizers), and crop damage by wild animals particularly elephants, as observed in Milola near the Selous Game Reserve. Since crops grown in one season do not sustain farmers to the next harvest season this indicates food insecurity to the household. Having a high number of households eating one to two meals a day indicates that food insecurity is prevalent in most Tanzania rural society and has been adopted as copying the strategy of food insecurity in most sub-Saharan African countries (Tsegaye et al., 2018).

Food insecurity is more prevalent in women-headed households possibly because they lack alternatives to another source of labor force, the burden of children and most are elderly and hence less energetic. Also, food insecurity is more for farmers compared to households who are either in formal or informal employment, this is because agricultural activities are much affected by the impacts of climate change compared to other activities and income gained in employment is used to buy food (Carson et al.,2020).

Increased susceptibility to food insecurity has led farmers to cultivate in the Mpondi wetland to gain food and sell crops to gain income since at least it is easy to carry local irrigation of crops during the dry season and this has been a tendency of most sub-Saharan countries in rural areas to

opt cultivation in wetland areas since in the climate change era wetland maintain wetness and fertility comparing to highland areas (Ngowi, 2020).

Contribution of wetland to food security and livelihoods

A vast majority of households depend on wetland resources for food security and livelihoods which is similar to studies conducted in other areas in Tanzania which show that most rural poor communities have been opting to cultivate in wetland areas since the areas maintain wetness even in the current trend of drought associated to climate change (Mahadevan et al.,2024; Dalahmeh et al., 2018). The study shows Mpondi wetland is utilized for food crops production such as beans, rice, cassava and peas while also utilized for the production of cash crops like sesame which is used as a means of gaining income that assists farmers in buying food, especially in the time of little harvest. Study conducted elsewhere in Tanzania indicate that wetlands are much utilized for food production and livelihoods means for instance, In Kilombero wetland, fishing and agriculture are the main activities for the peoples' livelihoods, where fishing contributes about Tshs 3.6 billion (US \$ 1565217.4) per year to the households 'income (Alavaisha, 2022).

It is also reported by Halima, & Munishi (2019) that approximately 75% of the households around Nyumba ya Mungu Dam depend on fishing activities for their livelihoods and food security. The research conducted by Nindi et al., (2014) indicated that about 83% of households in Idete and 93% in Signali village conduct crop farming in the wetlands, which contributes about 77% and 97% of their total annual incomes respectively. Studies elsewhere in Africa also indicate rural overdependence on wetland areas for food security and livelihoods for instance the Barotse floodplain in Zambia, 28,000 ha of cultivated land support about 27,500 households with an estimated income of \$ 2.34 million a year. Also, a large number of cattle are grazed in the floodplain (Banda, 2022).

In Rwanda, the wetlands of Cyabayaga support the production of rice which contributes to about an average of \$1,045 of income per household per season in a year (Turyahabwe et al.,2015). The overall dependence on wetland resources is mainly because wetland has some relatively higher levels of water/moisture content particularly in the dry season compared to highland areas and have some relatively higher levels of fertility due to the accumulation of sediments from highland areas. Hence with unreliable rainfall characterized by late onset and early cessation during the planting season and prolonged dry spells in some areas, which hinder crop growth, inevitably, rural

communities will largely rely on wetlands for food security and livelihoods, especially in the prolonged dry periods.

Ecological sustainability of the wetland

Although wetlands provide critical ecosystem services (provisioning, supporting, and regulating), as well as food security and livelihood benefits—particularly in the climate change era—they are increasingly threatened by overexploitation, raising uncertainty about their future sustainability. The findings indicate a marked decline in Mpondi wetland productivity compared to previous years, largely attributed to climate-induced drought and unsustainable agricultural practices. Furthermore, ecological degradation has disrupted habitats of soil and aquatic organisms, thereby diminishing ecosystem functionality. Materu et al. (2018) report similar ecological changes in Pangani and Kilombero wetlands caused by poor agricultural practices and settlement expansion. Thus, wetland resources must be utilized sustainably to preserve both ecological integrity and socioeconomic benefits for current and future generations.

5. Conclusions and recommendations

The study has shown that the Mpondi wetland is crucial for the food security and livelihoods of the Milola Community. Many Milola people are poor rural farmers who depend on wetlands to produce crops for food and income generation. However, currently, the wetland has reduced its capability to produce due to the drought in the valley caused by bad agricultural practices and climate changes, which has made it difficult to carry out farming activities without local irrigation. The study exemplifies how natural ecosystems, like wetlands, directly contribute to human well-being by providing essential services like food security and human livelihoods, however due to climate change and increasing population, the pressure over wetland resources has made reduction of wetland services and therefore the study demonstrate strategies for building climate change resilience in the agricultural sector, as a key concern for rural communities in Tanzania and globally. Also will help to adopt different approaches in management of wetland resources like Participatory approaches since local communities interact with and manage the wetland better than top down approaches since rural communities depending their livelihoods on these wetlands hence

they must carry their practices in a sustainable way. Lastly the study will contribute in addressing the sustainable development goals 1 no poverty, 2 zero hunger, and goal no 13 climate action.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors have no conflicts of interest to declare that are relevant to the content of this article

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